

A Gentle Introduction to General Purpose Artificial Intelligence Systems (GPAIS)

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- ❑ What are GPAIS?
- ❑ Definition and properties
- ❑ Taxonomy
- ❑ Generative AI and Multi-modality
- ❑ Discussion

The latest advances of AI

ChatGPT

Examples

"Explain quantum computing in simple terms" →

"Got any creative ideas for a 10 year old's birthday?" →

"How do I make an HTTP request in Javascript?" →

Capabilities

Remembers what user said earlier in the conversation

Allows user to provide follow-up corrections

Trained to decline inappropriate requests

Limitations

May occasionally generate incorrect information

May occasionally produce harmful instructions or biased content

Limited knowledge of world and events after 2021

Dall-E

**What are
GPAIS?**

Is this Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)?

- ❑ These systems have created lots of hype and fears
 - ❑ But an Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) doesn't quite exist (yet)
- ❑ The intelligence of current AI significantly differs from human intelligence
- ❑ They may be lacking some abilities: complex reasoning, consciousness, initiative, etc.
- ❑ They are great at others though (e.g. assembling patterns)

Logic Fail - Example from X/Twitter

Limitations of 'Traditional' Artificial Intelligence

- ❑ A traditional AI application:
 - ❑ Relies on experts to manually design and tune algorithms
 - ❑ Machine learning (ML) techniques, usually require a large amount of data to extract knowledge
 - ❑ Normally lack the generalisation ability to perform well on unseen tasks
- ❑ General-purpose AI systems aim to automate this process

Usual workflow to build an AI solution based on ML

GPAIS: What are they?

- ❑ No clear definition yet, but the term GPAIS may serve of:
 - ❑ A more **modest/realistic expectation** of AI with no expectation to have inherent human abilities
 - ❑ Best case scenario GPAIS could perform tasks it hasn't been trained for (**emergent abilities**)
- ❑ Terms like **foundation models** or **generative AI** are key to GPAIS, but not everything

GPAIS: previous definitions

- ❑ There are some issues with previous definitions
 - ❑ Some degree of disagreement
 - ❑ Use of AGI and GPAIS interchangeably
 - ❑ Very much focused on adaptation/transfer learning
 - ❑ Focus on legislation, but very little on how they are designed, the problems they can solve, and the challenges they are to address...

Our goal: from traditional AI to AGI

- Categorise GPAIS according to their degree of autonomy and expected capabilities

Properties

- ❑ What are GPAIS?
- ❑ Definition and properties
- ❑ Taxonomy
- ❑ Generative AI and Multi-modality
- ❑ Discussion

GPAIS: definition and properties

- **Fixed purpose AI:** would consider a **single task at a time** and would normally require having sufficient data to train a model.
 - Typically solve following the ML lifecycle
- **GPAIS:** multiple tasks are considered at once.
 - Intuitively, a more complex learning environment which aims to exploit synergies among tasks
 - Classical example: **multi-task learning**
- To really define what GPAIS, we involve **time** in the definition

GPAIS: definition and properties

- ❑ **Closed-world:** Assumes we have data for a number of tasks, and those will be the only tasks
- ❑ **Open-world:** New tasks may arise (fewer data is common)

❑ **Data availability:**

- ❑ In closed-world, we generally expect sufficient data (preprocessing may be needed though)
- ❑ In open-world, data scarcity may become the norm for new tasks (exceptions like classical AutoML)

❑ **Performance on new tasks:**

- ❑ GPAIS may display difficulties, but not be aware of such difficulty
 - ❑ Results in **hallucinations** and **untrue statements**
- ❑ Conversely, may perform well unexpectedly (**emergent abilities**)

Advanced GPAIS: expectations

- Response to new tasks more robustly/positively via self-diagnosis.

From Advanced GPAIS to AGI

- Difficult to say what's left to realise AGI, but we enumerate the following we know are kind of difficult for current GPAIS:
 - Complex reasoning
 - Exploit causality
 - Curiosity to explore new tasks
 - 'Conscience' of themselves
 - ...

A Taxonomy of methods

Taxonomy of methods

To enable General-Purpose AI Systems (GPAIS) we observe two distinct approaches:

- ❑ **AI-powered AI:** we add a new layer of abstraction that would an AI algorithm to either **design** or **enrich** another AI
- ❑ **Single-model:** create only one model that learns from various tasks and/or vast amounts of data, namely, multi-task and foundation models.
- ❑ Hybridisation of the above two are definitely possible

H. Song, I. Triguero, E. Özcan, A review on the self and dual interactions between machine learning and optimisation, Progress in Artificial Intelligence, 8:143-165, 2019.

GPAIS at a glance

- ❑ Key idea: add a new layer of abstraction
- ❑ **AI to design AI**
 - ❑ Hyper-parameter tuning
 - ❑ Model selection
 - ❑ Model construction
- ❑ **AI to enrich, help, or evolve AI algorithms**
 - ❑ Generative AI to create data useful to train AI models
 - ❑ Discovering new behaviours
 - ❑ ...

Automated Algorithm Selection

- ❑ **Common objective:** take the human out of the learning/optimisation process
- ❑ Different approaches may be suitable for closed or open-world settings
- ❑ Most existing approaches assume sufficient data in open-world (e.g. AutoWeka, AutoGluon, Auto-sklearn)
 - ❑ Meta-learning could **enable zero-shot learning**

AI-powered AI: enriching AI

Discovering new behaviours

- ❑ **Challenge:** adapt dynamically to changes in the environments (e.g. data distribution shifts)
- ❑ Well known challenge in data streaming, with drift detectors strategies -> would probably class as closed-world
- ❑ Continual learning in Neural Networks may use reinforcement learning and meta-learning to help identify changes, and avoid catastrophic forgetting

Discovering new behaviours

Data generation

Data generation

- ❑ **Challenge:** Lack of data that could resemble the open world
- ❑ The emergence of generative models allows us to generate lots of artificial data that could help train other AI systems
 - ❑ POET is a prime example of environment generation to improve generality in open-world scenarios

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D1WWWhQY9N4g>

Wang et al. Paired Open-Ended Trailblazer (POET): Endlessly Generating Increasingly Complex and Diverse Learning Environments and Their Solutions. arXiv, (1901.01753), 2019.

Learning to learn

- ❑ **Challenge:** Need for lots of data to learn
- ❑ **Opportunity:** having many somehow related tasks may be useful to **learn how to learn**
- ❑ Meta-learning strategies can be used in those scenarios (**few-shot learning**)
- ❑ Mimics human learning extracting meta-knowledge from a collection of few-shot learning tasks, and transfer it to unseen tasks
 - ❑ Inherently open-world!

Active learning

Active learning

- ❑ **Challenge:** Detect they are wrong and seek human intervention
- ❑ Active learning is normally used to reduce annotation efforts
- ❑ Potentially useful in GPAIS when the demand for new annotated data is autonomously decided by the model itself
- ❑ Could lead to advanced open world systems

Fang et al. Active Multitask Learning With Trace Norm Regularization Based on Excess Risk. IEEE Trans. on Cybern., 47(11):3906–3915, 2017.

Cooperative and collective learning

- ❑ **Challenge:** Mitigate the weaknesses of isolated AI models
- ❑ Models to help each other, constituting a larger, general purpose system (not really a new research topic)
- ❑ E.g. Different AI models could focus on different data modalities or tasks to address complex problems
- ❑ Somehow related to Federated Learning and Swarm Intelligence

Cooperative and
collective
learning

Foundation models

- ❑ **Key idea:** train a model on a very large amount of data (typically for many tasks), and a later stage fine tune it to tackle new tasks
 - ❑ Very much for Deep Learning and transfer learning
- ❑ **Challenge:** How to exploit vast amounts of unlabelled data effectively?
 - ❑ Via traditional semi-supervised
 - ❑ **Self-supervision** (e.g. masking out words/pieces of an image)
- ❑ Large Language Models and Large Vision Models are based on this!

Generative AI and multi- modality

- ❑ ChatGPT, Midjourney, Dall-E, ..., they are called **generative AI** because they do generate text, audio, images, or even video.
- ❑ GenAI may be useful to help other AI as they learn the distribution of a dataset, generating data that resembles the original data
 - ❑ GANs were precursors of this kind, but not general purpose
 - ❑ LLMs generate content similar to original texts
 - ❑ For images, Diffusion Models (DMs) capture a higher level semantic meaning of a group of images, allowing text-to-image generation
- ❑ Both LLMs and DMs are, in essence, foundation models

Generative AI: the landscape

- ❑ This is changing on a daily basis, so it's difficult to be up to date!
 - ❑ They all keep adding new functionality
- ❑ Most famous DMs include Dall-E, Stable Difussion XL, and Midjourney
- ❑ In LLMs, Chat-GPT (4), Llama 2 and Google Bard
 - ❑ Llama (from meta) does provide the model, so we can play with it directly, fine-tuning it
 - ❑ ChatGPT allows for fine tuning, but not giving you the model

Multi-modality

- ❑ Being able to exploit different kinds of data (i.e. text, audio, video) is a way to make AI learn more similarly to the way we learn
- ❑ A multi-modal AI model can generate both a description of an image and an image based on text input
- ❑ GPT4 is now able to process images as well
- ❑ Google Gemini is a new LLM capable of processing text, images, code, and audio

User What is unusual about this image?

Source: [Barnorama](#)

GPT-4 The unusual thing about this image is that a man is ironing clothes on an ironing board attached to the roof of a moving taxi.

Agents meet LLMs

- W
- LL
- Ke
- Ex

```
(base) → gpt_engineer git:(main) x
```


ep

Hui Yang, Sifu Yue, and Yunzhong He. Auto-GPT for Online Decision Making: Benchmarks and Additional Opinions. *arXiv*, (2306.02224), 2023.

Discussion and conclusions

Current status and prospects of GPAIS

- ❑ LLMs (and soon LVMs) are currently the most prominent GPAIS that display some degree of general intelligence
- ❑ But, generalising better has been thoroughly study in AI, and many ideas could be borrowed to further improve those systems
- ❑ The proposed taxonomy is not a sharp separation separation across methods, and hybrid methods will enable more advanced GPAIS (e.g. active learning for LLMs – there is already a bit implemented in there)

- ❑ Hot topics for current GPAIS:
 - ❑ **Hallucinations** (and self-awareness of their limitations)
 - ❑ Factual errors, invented details, biases... debugging why they happen and define strategies to solve them
 - ❑ They may not always be ‘a bad thing’, don’t we become creative when we don’t know they answer?
 - ❑ The problem may lie in the confidence/awareness
 - ❑ **Emergent abilities**
 - ❑ It is still unclear whether these are real or not, and why they occur... explainable AI may help?

Implications to our society

- ❑ Making AI more general and independent is becoming one of the biggest worries of our current society.
- ❑ Although we may be far from AGI, this calls for an ethical and responsible design of General Purpose systems
- ❑ **Trustworthy AI** is needed (no hallucinations!)
- ❑ Sustainability – GPAIS like ChatGPT demand way too much energy

Regulation and governance

- ❑ Governance frameworks with regulation and trustworthiness need to be developed . The EU AI Act is the most advanced regulation
- ❑ Closed-world may be more manageable than open-world, as this setting may be more difficult to **audit**

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